

CONTRASTIVE STUDY OF PROVERB EQUIVALENCE

Abdukhayumova Sanobar Abdurashidovna

PhD student at TerSU, Foreign philology faculty

Abduqayumovasanobar1997@gmail.com

Uralova Oysuluv Poyan khizi

Scientific supervisor: PhD , dots.

Annotation: This article stresses the contrastive studies on proverb equivalences in different languages and explains similarities and differences that exist between proverbs in a foreign language and their mother tongue. Besides, types of equivalences of proverbs are described and the examples are given.

Key words: types of equivalences of proverbs, contrastive studies , grammatical and lexical differences.

Phraseological equivalence presents an intensively studied field (Korhonen, 2007; Dobrovol'skij, 2011), and a number of authors have recently stressed the complexity of the issue by outlining different approaches of contrastive idiom research (Farø, 2006; Menado-Blanco, 2010). The present article does not focus on equivalence as an abstract property used to describe the aimed-at quality of a target text in the translation (Koller, 2004), but instead is concerned with the existence of equivalents, i.e. of proverbs that can be regarded as identical or at least corresponding, and which serve as substitutes in two languages.

The contrastive perspective is helpful in making students aware of the similarities and differences that exist between proverbs in a foreign language and their mother tongue. Altogether four types of correspondence between L1 and L2 proverbs can be distinguished: Total equivalence, partial equivalence, zero-equivalence and pseudo equivalence. The reason for the existence of corresponding proverbs can be found in language contact and common sources. Examples of the former can be easily found due to the growing influence of English on European languages (Mieder, 2004a-c, 2010; Fiedler, 2006, 2010, 2012b; Rozumko, 2012b). With regard to common sources, identical or similar proverbs can be traced back to mythological stories, classical literary works (e.g., Shakespeare, Dante, Cervantes), folk narrations, fables and legends (Piirainen, 2010: 12; 2012). Among those internationally known loan translations are One hand washes the other, One swallow does not make a summer and All's well that ends well. Equivalents are not restricted

to European languages, however. Paczolay's 1997 work registers equivalents of Like father, like son and Walls have ears in 46 languages each, including Chinese and Japanese and Arabic, Persian, Chinese, and Japanese respectively.

The group of partial equivalents encompasses proverbs with minor structural and/or lexical differences. The biblical warning "Pride goes before destruction, and

a haughty spirit before a fall" is known with the indefinite or definite article in English (Pride comes before a fall) and only with the definite article in German (Hochmut kommt vor dem Fall). The English proverbs A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush is known in German with the same imagery basis, but different constituents, as *Lieber den Spatz in der Hand als die Taube auf dem Dach* [ww: Better a sparrow in the hand than a pigeon on the roof]. For the foreign language learner and user those minor grammatical and lexical differences can cause central problems as structural stability can be a decisive precondition of the proverbial character of an expression.

A further constellation is the lack of equivalents, i.e. the situation that a proverb in one language has no correspondent proverb in the other. For example, the English *Every dog has its day* has no counterpart in German. As mentioned above, in a situation where one language exercises dominant influence on other languages such a constellation is often a starting point for loan processes.

Finally, there is the occurrence of pseudo-equivalents, which are normally termed false friends (*faux amis*). They have identical constituents and are based on the same image, but carry different meanings. In the questionnaire study the last straw turned out to be one for the students. The complete proverb. The last straw breaks the camel's back, which is rarely used today, would certainly not have caused problems. The popular reduction the last straw, however, made the participants remember the German expression with identical constituents, *der letzte Strohalm*, which is a false friend.

Students should know about these different types of equivalents to be alert to potential pitfalls. Here again it is on the level of the text that subtle differences become obvious and should be discussed. From a pragmatic point of view, the knowledge of equivalents and proverb parallels seems to be especially important, as

their use might be a way for non-native speakers to be expressive and creative without entering the social space of another speech community or merely aping native speakers. It can be very useful for learners to know about the existence and correct wording of a proverb that they know from their native language and are

therefore able to use adequately in the foreign language (Vajičková, 2000). In combination with the metacommunicative techniques described above (There is a proverb in my language ...) this might be a strategy to use colourful language, bring one's own culture and identity into the discourse and create a cooperative atmosphere by finding something that people have in common. The learner's individual proverb optimum should include some of those expressions, although they do not necessarily constitute the proverb minimum described above. For the two languages this chapter is focused on, this means that the following English proverbs are useful to know for German learners:

Constant dropping wears away the stone (German: Steter Tropfen höhlt den Stein) A burnt child dreads the fire (German: Ein gebranntes Kind scheut das Feuer) The apple doesn't fall far from the tree (German: Der Apfel fällt nicht weit vom Stamm) In wine is truth (German: Im Wein ist Wahrheit) Coming events cast their shadows before (German: Große Ereignisse werfen ihre Schatten voraus).

An important aim of foreign language teaching is to enable students to continue their acquisition as part of their individual studies. As phraseological units and proverbs are ubiquitous phenomena, as we said in they present an ideal subject for autonomous learning. Students should be encouraged to keep notebooks containing proverbs that they encounter outside the classroom (Irujo, 1993: 217) or to use worksheets, models of which Ettinger (2001) and Lüger (2004) prepared for French. In addition, several researchers (e.g. Ettinger, 2001; Bergerová [no year]) show didactic perspectives in combination with modern media (web-concordancer, Internet, CD-ROM) (see also Konecny et al., 2013).

References:

1. Korhonen, J. (2007). Probleme der kontrastiven Phraseologie. In H. Burger, D. Dobrovolskij, P. Kühn & N. R. Norrick (Eds.), *Phraseologie / Phraseology. Ein internationales Handbuch zeitgenössischer Forschung. An International Handbook of Contemporary Research* (pp. 574-589). Berlin/New York: de Gruyter.
2. Dobrovolskij, D. (2011). Cross-Linguistic Equivalence of Idioms: Does it Really Exist? In A. Pamies & D. Dobrovolskij (Eds.), *Linguo-Cultural Competence and Phraseological Motivation* (pp. 7-24). Baltmannsweiler: Schneider.
3. Farø, K. (2006). *Idiomatizität – Ikonizität – Arbitrarität. Beitrag zu einer funktionalistischen Theorie der Idiomäquivalenz. (Dissertation)* Copenhagen: University.

4. Mellado-Blanco, C. (2010). Die phraseologische Äquivalenz auf der System- und Textebene (am Beispiel des Sprachenpaares Deutsch-Spanisch). In J. Korhonen, W. Mieder & Piirainen, E. (Eds.), *Phraseologie global – areal – regional* (pp. 277-284). Tübingen: Gunter Narr.
5. Koller, W. (2004). *Einführung in die Übersetzungswissenschaft*. Wiesbaden: Quelle & Meyer.
6. Mieder, W. (2004a). Der frühe Vogel und die goldene Morgenstunde. Zu einer deutschen Sprichwortentlehnung aus dem Angloamerikanischen. In I. Hyvärinen, P. Kallio & J. Korhonen (Eds.), *Etymologie, Entlehnungen und Entwicklungen. Festschrift für Jorma Koivulehto* (pp. 193-206). Helsinki: Société Néophilologique.
7. Mieder, W. (2004c). 'Ein Apfel pro Tag halt den Arzt fern': Zu einigen amerikanischen Lehnssprüchwörtern im Deutschen. *Revista de Filologia Alemana*, 12 135-149.
8. Mieder, W. (2010). 'Many roads lead to globalization'. The translation and distribution of Anglo-American proverbs in Europe. In J. Korhonen, W. Mieder, E. Piirainen et al. (Eds.), *Phraseologie global – areal – regional. Akten der Konferenz EUROPHRAS 2008 vom 13.-16.8.2008 in Helsinki* (pp. 43-59). Tübingen: Gunter Narr.
9. Fiedler, S. (2006). „Willkommen zurück!“ – der Einfluss des Englischen auf die Phraseologie der deutschen Gegenwartssprache. In H. Burger & A. Häcki-Buhofer (Eds.), *Phraseology in Motion I. Methoden und Kritik* (pp. 451-465). Baltmannsweiler: Schneider-Verlag Hohengehren.
10. Fiedler, S. (2010). „Am Ende des Tages zählt die Performance.“ – Der Einfluss des Englischen auf die Phraseologie der deutschen Gegenwartssprache. In J. Korhonen, W. Mieder, E. Piirainen et al. (Eds.), *Phraseologie global – areal – regional. Akten der Konferenz EUROPHRAS 2008 vom 13.-16.8.2008 in Helsinki* (pp. 163-172). Tübingen: Gunter Narr.
11. Fiedler, S. (2012b). Der Elefant im Raum ... The influence of English on German phraseology. In C. Furiassi, V. Pulcini & F. Rodríguez González (Eds.), *The Anglicization of European Lexis* (pp.239-259), Amsterdam/Philadelphia: Benjamins.
12. Rozumko, A. (2012). English influence on Polish proverbial language. In C. Furiassi, V. Pulcini & F. Rodríguez González (Eds.), *The Anglicization of European Lexis* (pp. 261-277). Amsterdam/ Philadelphia: Benjamins.
13. Piirainen, E. (2010). Common Features in the Phraseology of European Languages: Cultural and Areal Perspectives. In: J. Korhonen, W. Mieder, E. Piirainen

et al. (Eds.), *Phraseologie. Global– Areal – Regional* (pp. 16-27). Tübingen: Gunter Narr.

14. Piirainen, E. (2012). *Widespread Idioms in Europe and Beyond*. Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang.

15. Irujo, S. (1993). Steering clear: Avoidance in the production of idioms. *IRAL XXXI* (3), 205-219.

16. Ettinger, St. (2001). Vom Lehrbuch zum autonomen Lernen. Skizze eines phraseologischen Grundkurses für Französisch. In M. Lorenz-Bourjot & H. Lüger (Eds.), *Phraseologie und Phraseodidaktik* (pp. 87-104). Wien: Edition Praesens.

17. Lüger, H. (2004). Idiomatic Kompetenz – ein realistisches Lernziel? *Thesen zur Phraseodidaktik. Beiträge zur Fremdsprachenvermittlung Sonderheft 7*, 121-169.